

Multiclass abusive language detection task – challenging Transformers with RNNs models

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Abstract

In this report, we investigated whether a carefully tuned RNN-based model can match Transformer performance on multiclass abusive language detection in tweets. Using the AbuseEval v1.0 / OLID datasets, we applied consistent preprocessing (tokenization, punctuation filtering, placeholder removal), vocabulary-limited vectorization, and used GloVe-Twitter embeddings. To mitigate class imbalance and improve minority-class learning we tested data augmentation (using contextual BERT model), focal loss, recurrent and spatial dropout, and class weighting. We experimented with several LSTM and BiLSTM configurations and selected Model 4, a BiLSTM with SpatialDropout1D (0.3), recurrent dropout (0.5) and focal loss ($\gamma=2.0$), as the best trade-off between stability and class-wise performance. Model 4 achieved a macro F1 ≈ 0.51 , comparable to the BERT baseline reported by Caselli et al. (2020): macro F1 ≈ 0.535 . Both architectures perform well on recognizing not abusive and explicitly abusive tweets, but implicit abuse detection remains problematic. Results suggest that an optimized RNN can be competitive with an older BERT baseline while being computationally lighter; future work should evaluate modern Transformer variants and richer contextual methods to better capture implicit abuse.

Keywords

Sentiment Analysis, Abusive Speech Detection, RNNs

1. Introduction

Some years after the publication of the paper *Attention Is All You Need* (Vaswani et al., 2017), research moved away from the previously state-of-the-art RNN-based models. This shift is evidenced by the proliferation of pre-trained Transformer models (e.g., the BERT family), which consistently outperform deep learning baselines due to their ability to handle “long-range dependencies efficiently [...], thereby setting new benchmarks in performance across a wide variety of NLU-based tasks” (Mandal, 2021). Therefore, approaching a multiclass sentiment analysis task such as the one selected for the final project of this course should naturally entail relying on Transformer-based architectures (Hafeez, 2026).

Nevertheless, we decided to address a multiclass classification task involving the categorization of tweets¹ creating a RNN-based model. This choice is motivated by two main reasons: first, the opportunity to learn through the discussion and design of every component of our RNN architecture; second, the possibility to challenge the results obtained by a BERT-based model on the same task, as reported in Caselli et al. 2020.

The addressed task consisted of a multiclass classification of English tweets to determine whether the abusiveness of the message, according to the following definition:

We define abusive language as hurtful language that a speaker uses to insult or offend another individual or a group of individuals based on their personal qualities, appearance, social status, opinions, statements, or actions (Caselli et al., 2020, p. 5)

The dataset of tweets used to train, validate, and evaluate our model was the AbuseEval v1.0 dataset (tommasoc80, 2023), an enriched version of the OLID dataset created for the OffenseEval shared task competition in 2019 (Zampieri et al., 2019). We adopted the annotation scheme

¹ i.e. what we would call now “posts on X” (formerly Twitter).

proposed by Caselli et al. (2020), which further subdivides the original Abusive class into two categories: implicit abuse and explicit abuse. These two categories were defined in the paper (p. 5) as follows:

- (a) *Explicit (abuse): it always has a surface evidence of abuse with respect to a target by means of profanity, performative constructions, imperatives, idioms, adjectives or nouns with a clear negative connotation;*
- (b) *Implicit (abuse): it does not have any surface evidence, abuse can only be suggested or inferred. It can be hidden with sarcasm, metonymy, irony, litotes, euphemism, and inside jokes among other linguistic devices*

In the same article, the authors report a table showing the results of the `uncased_L-12_H-768_A-12` pre-trained BERT model (Devline et al., 2019) fine-tuned for the same multiclass classification task using the same annotated dataset.

Table 1. Performance of `uncased_L-12_H-768_A-12` pre-trained BERT model.

Data set	Class	Precision	Recall	F1 (macro)
AbuseEval	NOTABU	0.864 ± .019	0.936 ± .013	0.535 ± .023
	IMP	0.234 ± .086	0.098 ± .092	
	EXP	0.640 ± .060	0.509 ± .139	

Whitin this framework, our hypothesis was that a RNN-based model could have achieved the same performance. Our result is a RNN model (Model 4) whose performance is very close to the `uncased_L-12_H-768_A-12` pre-trained BERT model, as shown in the conclusions.

It is important to note that the experiments reported in this essay represent only a subset of our broader exploration. Throughout the development process, we conducted numerous additional experiments, including variations in model architecture (e.g., different numbers and types of layers), alternative data augmentation strategies for both the IMP and EXP classes, and multiple techniques to mitigate overfitting. We also evaluated different combinations of these and other elements. For clarity and conciseness, in this report we focus on the most relevant and effective steps that led us to the best-performing configuration. All the code related to the following experiments is available at these links: [Colab – Part1](#) and [Colab – Part2](#).

2. Data

In this section we are going to describe how the dataset used to train our model was constructed, how the training set was analyzed to inform the model design, and which preprocessing steps were applied to optimize the training process. All the data that we used can be found and downloaded at [this Google Drive link](#).

First, we started by downloading the `olid-training-v1.0` dataset containing 13,240 annotated tweets following OLID scheme, along with the `testset-levela` dataset containing the tweets to be used as part of the test set (Zampieri et al., 2019). Both datasets were then uploaded to Google Colab and inspected as data frames. Next, we associated the tweets contained in the `testset-levela` and in the `olid-training-v1.0` datasets with the corresponding enriched labels from the AbuseEval v1.0 dataset.

At this stage, we examined the distribution of the AbuseEval labels within the `olid-training-v1.0` tweets (**Graph 1**). The resulting class distribution revealed a significant imbalance in the training data, with a clear predominance of non-abusive tweets (79.24% of the total), followed by explicitly abusive tweets (15.28%) and a smaller proportion of implicitly abusive tweets (5.48%).

Graph 1. Number of tweets per category in `olid-training-v1.0`

The next step in the inspection of the `olid-training-v1.0` dataset consisted of a closer examination of the most frequent words. The tweets were lowercased, tokenized using the NLTK tokenizer (Loper & Bird, 2002), and punctuation marks were removed. To speed up the process, we created a subset containing the first 1000 tweets and generated a frequency table (**Table 2**) using Python's `Counter` class.

Table 2. Raw frequency of the 10 MFWs in the first 1000 tweets

user	2354
url	169
liberals	121
gun	97
like	91
control	90
antifa	84
maga	79
conservatives	73
people	66

Since the training set was preprocessed to remove stopwords and punctuation, the same preprocessing steps were applied to the test set to ensure consistency. We chose to implement this to prevent data leakage and to guarantee that the model evaluates unseen data under the same conditions it was trained on.

Next, we moved to the creation of the validation set by allocating 20% of the `olid-training-v1.0` dataset through the `train_test_split` function from the `sklearn.model_selection` module. To ensure that the validation set remained representative of the original class distribution, we chose to apply a stratified sampling instead of a simple validation split. In fact, the latter method selects the last portion of the training data prior to shuffling and may therefore result in an unbalanced or unrepresentative distribution of classes, particularly for less frequent categories such as implicit abuse. The result is a validation set composed of 2119 instances, of which ~15% EXP, ~5 % IMP and ~80% NOTABU (see **Graph 4**).

Graph 4. Validation set – number of tweets per category

Finally, to prepare the data for multiclass classification, the train, validation and test labels were encoded using the `OneHotEncoder` from `scikit-learn`, transforming each label into a binary vector that indicates the presence of a particular class.

3. Experiments

All the experiments described in this section were implemented using Keras (Chollet et al., 2015), a high-level deep learning framework for Python that provides a user-friendly and modular interface for building, training, and evaluating neural network models.

Within this framework, we defined two utility functions: `training()` and `prediction()`. The training function trains the neural network on the provided data for a specified number of epochs, using a batch size of 32 and shuffling the data at each epoch to improve generalization. Validation data can be passed to monitor performance during training, and additional functionalities such as early stopping or model checkpoints can be implemented through the `callbacks_list`. The function returns the training history, including metrics such as loss and accuracy for both training and validation sets.

The prediction function uses the trained model to generate class predictions on the validation data in order to tune the hyper-parameters and compare the models. Since the model outputs probabilities in one-hot encoded form, the function applies the inverse transformation of the `OneHotEncoder` to convert these predictions back into the original class labels, providing an easily interpretable output for evaluation and analysis. At the end, we evaluate the chosen model on the unseen test data.

3.1. Preliminary attempts²

Some steps needed to be taken before starting building the models, namely the download and preparation of pre-trained embeddings and the definition of the vectorization layer function.

Firstly, to leverage prior knowledge from large-scale text corpora during the training, we applied transfer learning by using pre-trained word embeddings, confident that this could have helped our model to generalize better and converge faster compared to an approach of creating word representations from scratch. In particular, we chose the GloVe Twitter embeddings (`glove-twitter-200`), a 200-dimensional, uncased embedding model trained on 2 billion tweets comprising 27 billion tokens with a vocabulary of 1.2 million words (Pennington et al., 2014), created and maintained by the NLP Group at Stanford University. These embeddings are specifically trained on tweets, which makes them particularly well-suited for our corpus.

After having downloaded the embeddings, an embedding matrix was then created to match the vocabulary extracted from our training dataset. This means that each word in our vocabulary was assigned its corresponding pre-trained vector, while words absent from the embeddings were initialized as zero vectors. This matrix was subsequently used as the weight initialization for the model's embedding layer.

Secondly, to convert tweets into sequences of integer tokens suitable for input to the model, we used a `TextVectorization` layer from Keras. In particular, we defined the vectorization function with the following specifications: it standardizes text by lowercasing and removing punctuation, splits words on whitespace, and limits the vocabulary to the `max_words` most frequent tokens. Each tweet is then transformed into a fixed-length sequence of integers of length equal to `max_length`, with padding or truncation applied as necessary.

To optimize computational efficiency and trying to reduce the noise caused by infrequent tokens, the `max_words` figure was set to 9305, corresponding to 65% of the unique tokens in the training set that had a corresponding embedding in `glove-twitter-200`. For the same reasons, the tweets were padded or truncated to a maximum length of 50 tokens (`max_length=50`), a

² All the code related to this section can be found here: https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1Xqi44cuU-F8faRaV8WDEn_6XBd-C5fE9?usp=sharing

threshold determined by computing the 95% percentile of the tweet length distribution in **Graph 3**.

3.1.1. Model 1: LSTM 1x30x3

The core of the first model we implemented was a single Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network with 30 nodes. We chose to start with an LSTM structure because it is well suited to work with sequential text data, as it can capture both short and long-range dependencies between tokens. This feature is crucial for understanding the contextual and compositional nature of tweets.

The model is structured as follows: the input layer receives raw text strings, which are first processed by the previously defined `TextVectorization` layer. The vectorized sequences are then passed to an `Embedding` layer initialized with the pre-trained GloVe Twitter embeddings. The embedding layer is configured with `mask_zero=True` to ignore padding tokens during sequence processing and is kept non-trainable to preserve the original semantic information of the GloVe embeddings so to reduce the risk of overfitting.

The embedded sequences are then fed into a unidirectional LSTM layer with 30 nodes activated by the ReLU function. Finally, a fully connected `Dense` layer with `softmax` activation outputs a probability distribution over the three target classes (NOTABU, EXP, IMP).

The model is trained using the Adam optimizer and categorical cross-entropy loss, which is suggested for multiclass classification with one-hot encoded labels. To improve training robustness and prevent overfitting, several callbacks were employed. Early stopping was applied both on training accuracy and validation loss, with a patience of five epochs; in the latter case, the best-performing model weights were restored. Additionally, model checkpoints were saved at each epoch based on validation loss, and the `BackupAndRestore` callback was used to ensure training could be resumed seamlessly in case of interruptions.

Looking at the results, the graphs showing the loss and the accuracy evolution over the epochs of both the training set and the validation set show a clear overfitting of the model since the first epochs. In fact, while the train set performance improves, after a few epochs the validation set loss (**Graph 5**) and accuracy (**Graph 6**) remain overall stable over time.

Graph 5. Train and validation loss, Model 1

Graph 6. Train and validation accuracy, Model 1

The normalized confusion matrix (**Graph 7**) and at the standard classification metrics values (**Table 3**) shows a promising overall accuracy of the model with a 0.82 score. In particular, the NOTABU class was identified with very high precision (0.84) and recall (0.96), indicating that the model is particularly effective at recognizing non-abusive content. The EXP class obtained moderate performance, with a precision of 0.59 and

recall of 0.39. In contrast, the IMP class was not at all identified by the model, resulting in zero precision and recall.

Graph 7. Confusion matrix, Model 1

Table 3. Performance metrics, Model 1

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
EXP	0.59	0.39	0.47	405
IMP	0.00	0.00	0.00	145
NOTABU	0.84	0.96	0.90	2098
Accuracy			0.82	2648
Macro Average	0.48	0.45	0.45	2648
Weighted Average	0.76	0.82	0.78	2648

3.1.2. Model 2: LSTM 1x30x3 with recurrent dropout = 0.3

The total incapacity of Model 1 to predict the IMP class and the overfitting trend prompted us to try to mitigate these inefficiencies by applying recurrent dropout. This method randomly deactivates a fraction of the recurrent connections within the LSTM units during training, thereby preventing the model from relying too heavily on specific temporal patterns. The expected result was encouraging the network to learn more robust and generalizable representations of sequential dependencies, which is particularly important when dealing with minority classes such as IMP. Therefore, we added a recurrent dropout rate of 0.3 within the LSTM layer, whereas all other components remain unchanged from Model 1.

The results from the training loss and accuracy graphs don't show a significant change in the overfitting trend. Also, the confusion matrix (**Graph 8**) and the table with the performance metrics on the validation set (**Table 4**) show that the performance of the model remains almost overall unchanged.

Graph 8. Confusion Matrix, Model 2

Table 4. Performance metrics, Model 2

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
EXP	0.59	0.41	0.49	405
IMP	0.00	0.00	0.00	145
NOTABU	0.85	0.96	0.90	2098
Accuracy			0.82	2648
Macro Average	0.48	0.46	0.46	2648
Weighted Average	0.76	0.82	0.79	2648

In fact, the IMP class remains entirely unrecognized and the performances on NOTABU class remain overall unchanged too. For the EXP class, there's a slight improvement in the recall figure (from 0.39 to 0.41) showing that the model is a little bit less conservative in detecting this class.

Finally, also the overall F1-score remains almost unchanged, indicating that performance across classes did not substantially improve.

3.1.3. Model 3: BiLSTM 1x30x3 with recurrent dropout = 0.5

We then made another attempt by modifying the model architecture itself, moving from a unidirectional LSTM to a Bidirectional LSTM while simultaneously increasing the recurrent dropout rate to 0.5. This architectural change allows the model to process each tweet in both forward and backward directions, enabling it to capture contextual dependencies that may depend on both preceding and following tokens. At the same time, setting a higher recurrent dropout means that half of the recurrent connections within the LSTM units are randomly deactivated during training. This more aggressive regularization strategy was adopted to assess whether a richer contextual representation, combined with stronger regularization, could help the model recognize at least a small subset of tweets belonging to the IMP category.

The test results on the validation set weren't promising. As shown in **Graph 9** and **Table 5**, while precision for the EXP class slightly increases (from 0.59 to 0.63), this gain comes at the expense of a further reduction in recall (from 0.41 to 0.36), indicating that the model becomes more conservative in assigning the EXP label. Performance on the NOTABU class remains largely unchanged, with very high recall and stable precision, continuing to dominate the overall accuracy. The IMP class remains undetected while the macro-averaged recall metric show a marginal decline, suggesting that stronger recurrent regularization does not help the model capture minority-class patterns and may instead exacerbate the imbalance by further biasing predictions toward the majority class.

Graph 9. Confusion matrix, Model 3

Table 5. Performance metrics, Model 3

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
EXP	0.63	0.36	0.46	405
IMP	0.00	0.00	0.00	145
NOTABU	0.84	0.97	0.90	2098
Accuracy			0.82	2648
Macro Average	0.49	0.44	0.45	2648
Weighted Average	0.76	0.82	0.78	2648

3.2. Train dataset augmentation and further attempts³

After these first results, we realized that a more structural measure had to be taken to address the strong class imbalance present in the training data, particularly the under-representation of the implicitly abusive class. Therefore, we decided to apply data augmentation using the NLP augmentation library `nlpaug` (Ma, 2019). First, the `ContextualWordEmbsAug` augmenter was instantiated with a BERT-based model (`bert-base-uncased`) to perform context-aware word substitutions within tweets. Since our dataset contains relatively long texts (there are tweets of over 60 tokens and the median length is 16 tokens) we opted for this approach rather than a simpler data augmentation using non-contextual embeddings such as GloVe or Word2Vec. A new

³ All the code related to this section can be found here:

<https://colab.research.google.com/drive/13MjqpxLnktqvlIwrZLUYq8ZjjNTE23L?usp=sharing>

function, `augment_text()`, was defined to generate additional samples: it randomly selects tweets belonging to the minority class, applies the augmentation, and returns a new data frame containing the generated tweets labelled with the corresponding class.

Using this approach, we created 726 new IMP tweets, the same number of the starting IMP class. The augmented tweets were concatenated with the original training data to produce an expanded dataset with doubled IMP instances. At this stage the new dataset was inspected, showing that it contained 10491 NOTABU, 2023 EXP, and 1452 IMP tweets, as expected. To avoid an overrepresentation of the NOTABU class, we decided to randomly reduce its instances to 2500 samples. The final dataset was plotted (**Graph 10. Class distribution of the augmented dataset**) and saved as `abuseval_train_DOUBLE_IMP_2500_NOTABU`.

Graph 10. Class distribution of the augmented dataset

We chose not to further augment the IMP class to avoid overly aggressive data set manipulation that could compromise the quality of the training data and lead to overfitting. Conversely, we estimated that reducing the NOTABU class to 2500 instances would be a sound decision, as the remaining imbalance could be addressed by choosing other methods like focal loss or class weighting during model training.

Hence, after having encoded the new labels and created the validation set from the stratification of 20% of the new training set, we inspected the tweets of the training data frame to compute again the length distribution and the number of unique tokens in the tweets found in GloVe embeddings. As before, we used 65% of the most frequent tokens found in GloVe (= 6005) as reference figure for the `max_words` parameter in the vectorization layer.

Since the class distribution remains skewed after data augmentation, we decided to apply Focal Loss to further mitigate class imbalance by down-weighting well-represented examples and forcing the model to focus more on hard, misclassified instances (IMP in our case).

To apply this loss function, the labels must be provided in integer-encoded form rather than as strings or one-hot vectors. For this reason, we first mapped each class label to a unique integer identifier using the categories learned by the one-hot encoder. We then converted the training, validation, and test labels accordingly. The impact of the Focal Loss is defined by the `gamma` parameter, which controls the strength of the focusing effect applied to hard-to-classify examples. In fact, as `gamma` increases, “more importance is given to misclassified examples and very less loss will be propagated from easy examples” (Trivedi S., 2020).

3.2.1. Model 4: BiLSTM – Dense 1x30x30x3 with focal loss ($\gamma=2.0$)

After some attempts, we noticed that enriching the IMP class of the dataset and applying new methods like Focal Loss to give more importance to the less predicted classes were good, but insufficient practices. That’s why we decided to change the very structure of our model, making it more complex. We added to the Bidirectional LSTM of 30 nodes of Model 3 a fully connected Dense layer with 30 units and ReLU activation. The addition of a fully connected Dense layer had both experimental and theoretical reasons. We hypothesized that while the Bi-LSTM is responsible for capturing temporal dependencies within the tweet sequences, the additional Dense layer could have enabled a more flexible transformation of these representations before classification, potentially facilitating better separation between subtly different classes such as implicit and explicit abuse.

These changes in the structure resulted in a more sophisticated model increasing the risk of overfitting. To prevent this, we applied a `SpatialDropout1D` layer immediately after the embedding layer with a rate of 0.3. Unlike standard dropout, which randomly drops individual elements of the embedding vectors, “spatial dropout drops entire 1D feature maps instead of individual elements” ([Keras webpage](#)). This choice discourages the model from relying too heavily on specific embedding features.

As another countermeasure against overfitting, the recurrent dropout on the Bi-LSTM layer method was kept to a ratio of 0.5 and Focal Loss was implemented with a `gamma = 0.2`. Furthermore, the `EarlyStopping` callback with the `restore_best_weights` argument enabled was employed to automatically halt training when the optimal point was reached, reducing once again the risk of over-training the model and therefore overfitting.

The results of model 4 (**Table 6**) were way more promising than the previous attempts.

Graph 11. Confusion matrix, Model 4

Table 6. Performance metrics, Model 4

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
EXP	0.67	0.58	0.62	405
IMP	0.60	0.44	0.51	290
NOTABU	0.64	0.81	0.71	500
Accuracy			0.64	1195
Macro Average	0.64	0.61	0.61	1195
Weighted Average	0.64	0.64	0.63	1195

Compared to the previous models, these results show a clear shift in the model’s behaviour and a more balanced treatment of the classes. Most notably, this configuration is the first to successfully predict some instances of the IMP class, achieving a precision of 0.60 and a recall of 0.44. Although these values remain average in absolute terms, they represent a qualitative improvement over earlier models, which consistently failed to identify any implicit abuse.

Performance on the EXP class also changes substantially: recall increases markedly (from approximately 0.36–0.41 in the previous models to 0.58), indicating that the model is now better at retrieving explicitly abusive tweets. This improvement doesn’t affect the precision performances, suggesting an overall upgrading on the EXP class as confirmed by the confusion matrix (**Graph 11**) and the F1-score (from 0.46-49 to 0.62).

Performance on the NOTABU class slightly decreases, with both precision and recall dropping compared to earlier models, though remaining relatively high. This reduction reflects a deliberate shift away from over-optimizing the majority class in favour of improving minority-class recognition. Consequently, overall accuracy decreases from 0.82 to 0.64. However, macro-averaged metrics sensitively improve indicating a more equitable performance across classes and a better alignment with the objectives of multiclass abuse detection, where correctly identifying minority categories such as implicit abuse is crucial despite their limited frequency.

3.2.2. Model 5: BiLSTM – Dense 1x30x30x3 with focal loss ($\gamma=4.0$)

Although the great improvement of Model 4, the metrics of the performance related to the IMP class remained low. For this reason, we decided to increase the value of the Focal Loss gamma parameter from 2.0 to 4.0, trying to strengthen the focusing effect on hard-to-classify examples, particularly those belonging to the minority IMP classes. All the other settings of Model 4 remained unchanged. The results on the validation set show a slight downgrade in the overall performance (**Table 7**), especially regarding the increase of the false positive for the all the classes (**Graph 12**). The model’s behavior reflects a further shift of the model’s attention away from the majority class which doesn’t seem to be counterbalanced by an equal improvement in recognizing the IMP and the EXP classes. In fact, the results show a marginal improvement in the recall of the EXP class (from 0.58 to 0.59), while all the other figures decrease.

Graph 12. Confusion matrix, Model 5

Table 7. Performance metrics, Model 5

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
EXP	0.59	0.59	0.59	405
IMP	0.53	0.36	0.43	290
NOTABU	0.63	0.75	0.68	500
Accuracy			0.60	1195
Macro Average	0.58	0.56	0.57	1195
Weighted Average	0.59	0.60	0.59	1195

3.2.3. Model 6: BiLSTM – Dense 1x64x32x3 with focal loss ($\gamma=4.0$) and weighted training

At this stage, we decided to try to complexify the structure of our model hypothesizing that this could have helped detecting more subtle linguistic cues associated with implicit abuse in tweets. Nevertheless, this led to a risk of overfitting that we tried to contrast keeping the gamma of the Focal Loss to 4.0 but also incorporating class weights into the `SparseCategoricalFocalLoss` function.

These weights were computed using the `compute_class_weight` function from `sklearn.utils`, which assigns weights inversely proportional to the frequency of each class in the training data. As a result, errors in underrepresented classes contribute more heavily to the optimization process.

The results (**Graph 13** and **Table 8**) show a slight improvement in the metrics for EXP and IMP classes, in particular for what concerns the recall. The performance for EXP class remains stable

overall, with a decrease of the recall figures that is counterbalanced by an increase of precision. This outcome suggests that, even if the structure of this model is more complex, class weighting and focal loss increase the penalty for misclassifying IMP and EXP classes succeeding at improving the performances on these underrepresented categories, namely on the recall.

Graph 13. Confusion matrix, Model 6

Table 8. Performance metrics, Model 6

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
EXP	0.58	0.66	0.62	405
IMP	0.54	0.45	0.49	290
NOTABU	0.67	0.66	0.66	500
Accuracy			0.61	1195
Macro Average	0.59	0.59	0.59	1195
Weighted Average	0.61	0.61	0.61	1195

3.2.4. Models 7, 8 and 9: BiLSTM – Dense 1x24x24x3. Experimenting with Focal Loss and Spatial Dropout

Since the results of Model 6, which increased the number of nodes in both the LSTM and dense layers yield only partial improvements, we decided to take another direction by simplifying the architecture. In fact, in Model 7 we reduced the number of nodes in both BiLSTM and Dense layers (24 nodes each) while maintaining the spatial dropout (0.3) and the recurrent dropout (0.5) as countermeasures against overfitting. This reduction of complexity prompted us to remove the class weighting, relying solely on the Focal Loss ($\gamma = 4.0$) to address the remaining class imbalance.

The results of Model 7 (**Table 9**) confirm that the simplification of the model’s architecture alone does not lead to substantial performance gains over the previous configurations. For the IMP class, the model continues to struggle. While precision improves with respect to Model 6 (from 0.54 to 0.61), recall drops from 0.45 to 0.34, resulting in a lower F1-score of 0.44. In fact, the confusion matrix (**Graph 14**) shows that the predicted IMP tweets decrease suggesting that reducing the number of parameters and removing class weighting didn’t improve the model’s sensitivity to implicit abuse and may even slightly hinder it. Also, the slight decrease in the EXP label performance (F1-score from 0.62 to 0.60) together with the drop of precision (from 0.67 to 0.62) and the great improvement of recall (from 0.66 to 0.82) associated with the NOTABU category suggest that the model became less accurate and most likely to predict the most represented class instead of improving its performance on the two more challenging categories.

Graph 14. Confusion matrix, Model 7**Table 9.** Performance metrics, Model 7

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
EXP	0.62	0.57	0.60	405
IMP	0.61	0.34	0.44	290
NOTABU	0.62	0.82	0.70	500
Accuracy			0.62	1195
Macro Average	0.62	0.58	0.58	1195
Weighted Average	0.62	0.62	0.60	1195

At this point, we tried to expand our scope by examining the training dynamics of the BiLSTM-based models. Doing so, we observed that early stopping consistently occurred after a relatively small number of epochs, typically around ten. This behaviour suggested that the models might not have had sufficient time to fully exploit the training data before overfitting effects emerged. Based on this observation, we hypothesized that slowing down the learning process and further constraining overfitting could allow the model to learn more robust representations over a longer training horizon.

For this reason, we conducted an additional experiment starting from Model 7 as a baseline, increasing the SpatialDropout1D rate from 0.3 to 0.5. By dropping a larger proportion of embedding features during training, we gave more time to the model to train without prematurely overfitting. All other architectural and training parameters were kept unchanged in order to isolate the effect of this adjustment.

Despite the fact that this configuration trained for a longer period (17 epochs before early stopping) and exhibited closer alignment between training and validation loss and accuracy curves, the performance on the validation set (**Table 10** and **Graph 15**) does not show a meaningful improvement over Model 7. Compared to the previous model, the performance of the EXP class slightly improve in the recall metric (from 0.57 to 0.62). Also, the overall metrics for NOTABU class remain almost the same, with an F1-score of 0.70. As for the IMP class, although precision increases (from 0.61 to 0.69), recall noticeably decreases (from 0.34 to 0.26), resulting in a huge gap between these two figures and in a worsened F1-score (from 0.44 to 0.37). This indicates that the stronger spatial dropout leads the model to be even more conservative when predicting implicit abuse, reducing misclassifications but failing to recover additional true positives.

Our final experiment took Model 8 as the baseline. The aim was to preserve the longer effective training horizon observed in that configuration while improving the model's ability to detect the IMP class. In Models 7 and 8 we consistently observed a pattern for IMP: relatively high precision coupled with very low recall. This suggests the classifier is precise when it does predict IMP, but it fails to retrieve most IMP instances.

Graph 15. Confusion matrix, Model 8**Table 10.** Performance metrics, Model 8

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
EXP	0.62	0.62	0.62	405
IMP	0.69	0.26	0.37	290
NOTABU	0.61	0.83	0.70	500
Accuracy			0.62	1195
Macro Average	0.64	0.57	0.56	1195
Weighted Average	0.63	0.62	0.59	1195

To address this imbalance between precision and sensitivity, we reduced the focusing strength of the Focal Loss (halving γ). All other regularization and architectural choices from Model 8 ($\text{SpatialDropout1D} = 0.5$, $\text{recurrent_dropout} = 0.5$, Bidirectional LSTM and Dense layers with 24 nodes) were retained to keep the longer training dynamics while limiting overfitting.

Graph 16. Confusion matrix, Model 9**Table 11.** Performance metrics, Model 9

	Precision	Recall	F1-score	Support
EXP	0.57	0.70	0.63	405
IMP	0.60	0.33	0.42	290
NOTABU	0.66	0.72	0.69	500
Accuracy			0.62	1195
Macro Average	0.61	0.58	0.58	1195
Weighted Average	0.62	0.62	0.60	1195

The results contained in **Table 11** and **Graph 16** indicate that reducing the γ parameter of the Focal Loss doesn't achieve the intended effect of making the model less conservative, particularly with respect to the minority classes. Recall for the IMP class increases from 0.26 to 0.33 with respect to model Models 8, while precision decreases from 0.69 to 0.60 resulting anyway in a better F1-score (from 0.37 to 0.42) and a narrower gap between the two metrics. But if we compare these figures with Model 7 performances, we notice a slight decrease on the IMP class for all the figures (from an F1-score of 0.44 to 0.42). When looking at the other problematic class, EXP, we see that Model 8 outperforms the two previous models of only few decimal points. Therefore, lowering γ didn't substantially impact the performances of the model, as it is confirmed by the overall accuracy and the macro averaged metrics.

Finally, we created a reference table (**Graph 17**) showing an overview of the aforementioned performance metrics for the evaluated models described in the second part of the experiment section.

Graph 17. Overview of the performance metrics (from model 4 to 9)

4. Discussion and conclusion

When deciding what was the model with the best performances, we excluded the first three models from consideration. These initial approaches were trained before introducing data augmentation strategies and before adopting the BiLSTM + Dense-layer architecture. Although they achieved relatively high accuracy values, they were heavily biased toward the majority class and completely failed to detect the minority IMP class. Among the remaining models, Model 4 emerged as the best-performing configuration in terms of overall balance between classes and robustness of results. In fact, even if it doesn't have the best performances on the not abusive label, it offers a more equitable trade-off between majority and minority classes, which is essential in this task, where the correct identification of underrepresented categories such as implicit abuse remains critical despite their low prevalence.

To improve the possibility to derive meaning from context within the classes, exploiting the full potential of the GloVe pre-trained layer, we should consider in future works to avoid punctuation removal during dataset cleaning phase; in fact, punctuation can carry important pragmatic cues (e.g., emphasis, irony, or aggression) that are especially relevant for detecting forms of abuse.

Going back to our research question, the aim of this research was to falsify the null hypothesis stating that RNN-based models cannot achieve performance comparable to a Transformer-based model, namely the `uncased_L-12_H-768_A-12` BERT, on the task of multiclass abusive language detection in tweets. We therefore evaluated our best RNN model on the test set to assess its final performance on an unknown collection of tweets. The results demonstrate that Model 4 achieved macro F1 and class-level metrics that are competitive with those of BERT (Table 12), even if the macro F1 figure of the RNN-based model remains slightly lower. For both architectures, detecting implicit abuse remains challenging, reflecting the difficulty of this task due not only to the imbalanced dataset but also to the complex linguistic phenomena and subtle nuances that characterize implicit abusive language (ElSherief, 2021, p. 7).

Table 12. Comparison between Bert model and model 4 performance

Model	Class	Precision	Recall	F1 (macro)
<code>uncased_L-12_H-768_A-12</code> BERT	NOTABU	$0.864 \pm .019$	$0.936 \pm .013$	0.535 ± .023
	IMP	$0.234 \pm .086$	$0.098 \pm .092$	
	EXP	$0.640 \pm .060$	$0.509 \pm .139$	
MODEL 4	NOTABU	0.88	0.89	0.513
	IMP	0.21	0.11	
	EXP	0.46	0.58	

Finally, it is worth noting that our benchmark, the performance of the `uncased_L-12_H-768_A-12` BERT model, reported by Caselli et al. (2020), dates back to 2020. Since then, BERT architectures and training techniques have evolved considerably, potentially enabling better results with current Transformer-based models. For this reason, future research could explore how more recent Transformer architectures, pre-training strategies, and fine-tuning techniques perform on implicit abuse detection, providing a more up-to-date benchmark against which RNN-based models can be evaluated.

Bibliographic References

- Caselli T., Basile V., Mitrović J., Kartoziya I., Granitzer M. (2020). *I Feel Offended, Don't Be Abusive! Implicit/Explicit Messages in Offensive and Abusive Language*. In Proceedings of the Twelfth Language Resources and Evaluation Conference, pp. 6193–6202, Marseille, France. European Language Resources Association. Link: <https://aclanthology.org/2020.lrec-1.760/>
- Devlin, J., Chang, M.-W., Lee, K., Toutanova, K. (2019). *BERT: Pre-training of deep bidirectional transformers for language understanding*. In Proceedings of the 2019 Conference of the North American Chapter of the Association for Computational Linguistics: Human Language Technologies, Volume 1 (Long and Short Papers), pp. 4171–4186, Minneapolis, Minnesota, June. Association for Computational Linguistics. DOI: [10.18653/v1/N19-1423](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/N19-1423)
- ElSherief M., Ziems C., Muchlinski D., Anupindi V., Seybolt J., De Choudhury M., Yang D. (2021). *Latent hatred: A benchmark for understanding implicit hate speech*. arXiv. Link: <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2109.05322>
- Hafeez F., Hafeez M., Shaff Bin Imran M., Qasim A., Hussain N., Ahmad F., Sidorov G. (2026). *A Comparative Study of Deep Learning and Transformer Models for Twitter Sentiment Analysis*. In International Journal of Combinatorial Optimization Problems and Informatics, 17 (1), pp. 85–89. Link: <https://doi.org/10.61467/2007.1558.2026.v17i1.1241>
- Mandal R., Chen J., Becken S., Stantic B. (2021). *Empirical Study of Tweets Topic Classification Using Transformer-Based Language Models*. In Nguyen, N.T., Chittayasothorn, S., Niyato, D., Trawiński, B. (eds) Intelligent Information and Database Systems. ACIIDS 2021. Lecture Notes in Computer Science, vol 12672. Springer, Cham. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-030-73280-6_27](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-73280-6_27)
- Pennington J., Socher R., Manning C. D. (2014). *GloVe: Global Vectors for Word Representation*. In Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP), pp. 1532–1543, Doha, Qatar. Association for Computational Linguistics. DOI: [10.3115/v1/D14-1162](https://doi.org/10.3115/v1/D14-1162)
- Trivedi S. (2020), *Understanding Focal Loss – A Quick Read*. In VisionWizard. Link: <https://medium.com/visionwizard/understanding-focal-loss-a-quick-read-b914422913e7>
- Vaswani A., Shazeer N., Parmar N., Uszkoreit J., Jones L., Gomez A. N., Kaiser Ł., Polosukhin I. (2017). *Attention is all you need*. In I. Guyon, U. Von Luxburg, S. Bengio, H. Wallach, R. Fergus, S. Vishwanathan, & R. Garnett (Eds.), *Advances in neural information processing systems* (Vol. 30). Curran Associates, Inc. DOI: [10.48550/arXiv.1706.03762](https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1706.03762)
- Zampieri M., Malmasi S., Nakov P., Rosenthal S., Farra N., Kumar, R. (2019). *SemEval-2019 Task 6: Identifying and categorizing offensive language in social media (OffensEval)*. In Proceedings of the 13th International Workshop on Semantic Evaluation. pp. 75–86, Minneapolis, Minnesota, USA. Association for Computational Linguistics. DOI: [10.18653/v1/S19-2010](https://doi.org/10.18653/v1/S19-2010)

Datasets and online resources

- Chollet F., & others. (2015). *Keras*. GitHub. <https://github.com/fchollet/keras>
- Keras webpage, *SpatialDropout1d* layer. Link: https://keras.io/api/layers/regularization_layers/spatial_dropout1d/
- Loper E., Bird S. (2002). *NLTK: The Natural language toolkit*. arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.cs/0205028>
- Ma E. (2019). *NLP augmentation* [Computer software]. GitHub. <https://github.com/makcedward/nlpaug>
- tommasoc80. (2023). *tommasoc80/AbuseEval: v1.0 (v1.0)*. Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8372818>

Links to code and data

- Colab – Part1. https://colab.research.google.com/drive/1Xqj44cuU-F8faRaV8WDEN_6XBd-C5fE9?usp=sharing
- Colab – Part2. <https://colab.research.google.com/drive/13MjqpoxLnktqvlIwrZLUYq8ZjjNTe23L?usp=sharing>
- Data: [https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/17eQ6nAz4LQMjHT4HYaiEIPNQBw-f-uT0?usp=drive link](https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/17eQ6nAz4LQMjHT4HYaiEIPNQBw-f-uT0?usp=drive_link)